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**How the media became a tool of cultural hegemony for an authoritarian regime in
Bangladesh**

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Submitted in partial fulfillment of

JTC 602: Social & Cultural Communication Theory

course requirements

Scholars and political analysts argue that Bangladesh has got an authoritarian regime [Bangladesh Awami League (BAL) party led government] ruling the country for more than a decade, significantly restricting people's right to suffrage, freedom of expression and all other human rights (Kabir, 2022; Riaz, 2021). Gramsci's cultural hegemony theory stipulates that power is produced through hegemony. Gramscian cultural hegemony is established in a society when the "spontaneous consent given by the great masses of the population to the general direction imposed on social life by the dominant fundamental group," and the domination comes through an "intellectual or moral leadership." Dominant group attains the domination over "subaltern classes" even before and after assuming power, exploiting ideological tool. As per Gramscian thoughts, the press is the "most dynamic part" of the ideological structure that influences or is able to influence the public opinion. Bangladesh's media have allegedly been ideological allies of the ruling Awami League and remained uncritical of the party when the country needed it most. Applying Gramscian thoughts of cultural hegemony, the paper, relying on a textual analysis of selected media content from newspaper articles to video content in a qualitative approach, explores how the country's media provided the ideological-intellectual structure to the ruling BAL to establish its cultural hegemony. As the study shows the country's media worked as a hegemonic tool for the authoritarian regime, the study findings would help us understand the reason/s behind the sustenance of an authoritarian regime in the present-day context.

Media in Bangladesh

According to the 2016 National Media Survey (NMS), after television, print is the second most widespread media in the country with 23.8 percent readership (Azad, n.d.). With 30 television stations, 29 of them private, are in operation, the television channels have got as much

as 82.9 percent viewership in 2016 and the viewership is increasing persistently (Azad, n.d.). After the fall of military dictatorship in 1990, Bangladesh has witnessed a proliferation of television channels since late mid 1990s, thanks to the popularity of news bulletin in the private TV stations. A dozen more TV licenses have been issued while four TV stations were shut down in recent times (Azad, n.d.). The National Media Survey shows that the viewership has got doubled from 42 percent of 1998 to 82.9 percent in 2016 as the gap between urban and rural viewership has narrowed down, thanks to the spread of electrification across the country (Azad, n.d.).

In January 2018, Bangladesh has got a total of 3,025 registered newspapers across the country and 1,191 of them are daily newspapers. Of them, 470 are national dailies published from capital city Dhaka and a total of 32 are English-language dailies most of which are published from Dhaka. The number of weeklies is equally high. As many as 1,175 registered weeklies are being published from different places of the country. According to various estimations, the total Bengali newspaper circulation is around 1.5 million copies. Ten leading national newspapers have over 90 percent of the circulation. English circulation is also low, around 70,000. Like the Bengali circulation, mostly the residents of the capital and cities are the buyers of English newspapers.

Gramscian Cultural Hegemony

Dictionaries refer to hegemony as a domination of one state over others in respect to political, economic and military predominance. A bit more elaborative definition refers to a type of domination primarily achieved through people's consent as opposed to domination through coercion. The idea is often used to indicate complete domination, although it has a far more analytical power (Houssay-Holzschuch, 2020). Italian thinker Antonio Francesco Gramsci

redefined hegemony as a domination achieved through intellectual and moral leadership (Kurtz, 1996). Culture was central to Gramsci's idea of revolution (Kurtz, 2001). He argued that culture is a political product of intellectuals who shape the people's culture through ideological indoctrination (Kurtz, 2001).

Scholars argue that the dominant groups or class in the capitalist society employs various strategies to obtain that "subconscious consent" for maintaining a hegemonic power. Adorno and Horkheimer (1944) argue that the ruling group obtains domination in society by producing "popular culture" through its "culture industry" like films, radio programs, magazines, etc. While Artz & Murphy (2000) and Lears (1985) posit that the domination is achieved through "soft power", i.e. through ideology, McCoy, in reference to Foucault, says power of domination comes through knowledge. They consider the "subconscious consent" by the mass people or the subalterns is the key component for establishing hegemony or domination by the ruling/dominant groups or class to maintain the order or to maintain their supremacy in society (Adorno & Horkheimer, 1944; Lears, 1985; McCoy, 1988). Antonio Gramsci (1971) in his theory of cultural hegemony argues that the (capitalist) state and ruling class or bourgeoisie use cultural institutions to maintain power in societies. In place of violent or coercive process, in Gramsci's view, the bourgeoisie develops a hegemonic system to produce certain culture cashing in on ideology. This cultural hegemonic system continuously produces *consent* in favor of the ruling class (bourgeoisie) to maintain the status quo or to ensure the domination of the ruling class. The premise of Gramsci's cultural hegemony theory is that the domination comes with the subconscious consent from *subalterns* or from the masses as the ideology being produced by the hegemonic apparatuses like media of the ruling or dominant groups galvanize the opinion of subalterns stealthily over the course of time. Gramsci (1971) argues the ruling groups must attain

the domination over “subaltern classes” even before assuming the state power, and after assuming the state power to continue to the domination. In Gramsci’s eyes, ideas and beliefs are shaped in the public sphere where bourgeois hegemony is reproduced in cultural life through the media and other ideological state apparatuses to manufacture consent and legitimacy (Heywood, 1994). Scholars argue that the society must fulfill conditions for the hegemony (Artz & Murphy, 2000). The condition is there should be some hegemonic structures/tools/apparatus which will work like a machine to produce knowledge surrounding any ideology and then power to dominate. The press (Gramsci, 1985), films, magazines, books, (Adorno & Horkheimer, 1944), and political structures (Lears, 1985) are the components of the hegemonic structures. Gramsci posits that the supremacy of a certain class or group in a given society is manifested either in “domination” or in “intellectual or moral leadership.” Gramsci finds the press to be the “most dynamic part” of the ideological structure that influences or is able to influence public opinion (Gramsci, 1985, p. 390). Gramscian thoughts can be applied in a variety of intellectual traditions in various societies as the article explicates the concept of cultural hegemony in a variety of historical and intellectual contexts as the consent and the force interacts (Lears, 1985) as power is “productive,” “coercive,” “situational” and “pervasive” and the theory of power “lies dormant in the cultural studies” (McCoy, 1988).

Hegemonic Ideology in Bangladesh

Shortly after Gramsci’s idea of cultural hegemony became available in English language in early 1970s, scholars ardently received his concept of hegemony as “an important tool for cultural analysis and social critique” and they found many possibilities in it (Artz and Murhpy, 2000, p. 1). Drawing on Gramsci’s idea of cultural hegemony, some scholars define hegemony as “a process of moral, philosophical, and political leadership that a social group attains only

with the active consent of other important social groups” (Artz and Murphy, 2000, p. 1). The way the authoritarian regime in Bangladesh has been maintaining the status quo which can be called a kind of rhetorical legitimacy for 13 years, it appears that they have achieved the subconscious consent of domination by creating a cultural hegemony in the Bangladesh’s public sphere. The rhetorical legitimacy is often observed when it is seen that country’s public intellectuals rally behind the authoritarian regime and autocrat Sheikh Hasin’s rallies are attended by millions of people (“PM seeks vote for boat at massive Ctg rally,” 2022). When the western countries including US, UK and EU have started pushing for a fair general election in Bangladesh (Abdi, 2022; Chowdhury, 2022; “US expresses concern about police violence, opposition intimidation,” 2022), country’s public intellectuals have started criticizing western diplomats (“Eminent citizens criticise US envoy to Bangladesh,” 2022). It can be assumed that the authoritarian regime of Bangladesh Awami League (BAL) has been able to rally support for staying in power thanks to a hegemonic ideology centering on the country’s liberation which is the spirit of liberation or *Muktijuddher Chetona* in local parlance. *Muktijuddher Chetona* is a discursive frame coined by BAL and its socio-cultural wing which is essentially a particular interpretation of the liberation war and the current political trajectory (Riaz, 2015). The most significant part of this frame is not the frame itself, rather it is its critiques. Any critique of any issues of *Muktijuddher Chetona*, i.e. the liberation war, its organization, essence and outcome is considered against *Muktijuddher Chetona* and anybody who do the critiques are labeled as an anti-liberation element and the enemy of Bangladesh (Riaz, 2015).

Bangladesh has got a unique confrontational political system ever since it seceded from Pakistan in 1971 and the national identity has been the apple of discord in country's politics with a trickle-down effect in every stratum of society (Hossain, 2015; Rahman, 2019). Many argue

that Bangladesh would never be separated from West Pakistan sans Indian's interference (Hashmi, 2022). A group of people as well as some political parties such as Jamaat-e-Islami opposed the secession from Pakistan, fearing Indian hegemony over Bangladesh after the secession. Sheikh Mujibur Rahman, popularly known as Bangabandhu (friend of Bengal), is considered the founding father of Bangladesh. A group of people of Bangladesh believe that the birth of Bangladesh was impossible without Sheikh Mujib (Tahmid, 2021). Some scholars, however, argue that Sheikh Mujib did not want the break-up of the then Pakistan (Ahmad, 2014; Khandaker, 2014; Milam, 2019). In this wake, Bangladesh, since its birth, inherited a debate over Bangladesh's national identity, which is still haunting Bangladesh's society and politics. Bangladesh's society has been polarized over the question of nationalism, resulting in a sustained political instability and uncertainty in the country (Hossain, 2015; Maniruzzaman, 2017). "Should they be called Bangladeshi or Bengali?" is a longstanding question in the political discourse of Bangladesh. This has made country's political structure divided into two camps. Two major political parties – the Bangladesh Nationalist Party (BNP) and the Bangladesh Awami League (BAL) – lead the two rival camps. The BNP pursues politics based on 'Bangladeshi nationalism' – an idea broached by BNP founder and former president Ziaur Rahman while its rival BAL does politics based on 'Bengali nationalism' which is said to be the idea based on which Bangladesh's liberation war was waged (Rahman, 2018). Some analysts also argue that Muslim culture often clashes with Bengali culture which has its origin in Hindu culture (Bhattacharya, 2021; Maniruzzaman, 2017; Sakib, 2013; Salam, 2022). Anyone can know who belong to which camp by just knowing their socio- political slogans – *Bangladesh Jindabad* (Live long Bangladesh) versus *Joy Bangla* (Victory of Bangla) (Kallol, 2020; Uz-Zaman, 2019). Bangladeshi nationalist camp uses *Bangladesh Jindabad* slogan while Bengali

nationalist camp uses *Joy Bangla*. It will be worthy to note that with the BAL is in power for more than a decade, the High Court of the country has recently declared *Joy Bangla* as Bangladesh's national slogan ("Joy Bangla' national slogan: High Court," 2020). While the *Joy Bangla* camp sees India their closest friend and often remain busy to 'appease' or respect India as a show of their gratefulness toward India for its 1971 role, the *Bangladesh Jindabad* group often sees India skeptically (Hashmi, 2015; "India should remember what we've given: Hasina," 2018). *Joy Bangla* camp often calls *Bangladesh Jindabad* camp as pro-Pakistani while *Jindabad* camp often calls *Joy Bangla* camp as pro-Indian (Bari, 2017; "Go to Pakistan: PM tells Khaleda, accuses her of instigating army," 2013; Liton, 2015; Sarker, 2018; ভারতের দালাল আওয়ামী লীগ (□ছাত্রলীগের কুকর্ম□)[Indian Collaborator Awami League (Mischief of Chhatra League)], n.d.).

the BAL president and current prime minister Sheikh Hasina considers BNP founder Ziaur Rahman and his wife BNP's current chairperson Khaleda Zia the killer of his father (Somoy TV, 2021). Hasina often asks her nemesis Khaleda Zia to go Pakistan claiming that Khaleda and her allies do not belong to Bangladesh rather they, in her view, belong to Pakistan ("Go to Pakistan: PM tells Khaleda, accuses her of instigating army," 2013; "Punish Those Who Still Love Pakistan, Says Bangladesh PM Sheikh Hasina," 2018; Raju, 2019; Somoy TVa, 2022; Somoy TVb, 2022; "উনি পেয়ারে পাকিস্তানে চলে যেতে পারেন'," 2014).

The BAL-led authoritarian regime appears to keep this division alive in Bangladesh society using *Muktijuddher Chetona* (Riaz, 2021). The concept has been used by the BAL and its socio-cultural wings and activists including their traditional intellectuals as "an indicator of patriotism and unqualified support to the incumbent government" (Riaz, 2021, p. 192). The BAL always calls themselves to be the sole champion of the country's liberation and the savior of *Muktijuddher Chetona* and call others to be the enemy of Bangladesh (Bergman, 2016; Khan,

2019; Parvez, 2019). The 1971 liberation war has been the primary capital of the politics of the BAL (Hossain, 2018). Ever since it came to power in 2009, the BAL launched a campaign of *Muktijuddher Chetona* ostensibly to justify its move toward authoritarian one-party rule (Bergman, 2016). On the other hand, the boundary of the concept *Muktijuddher Chetona* – the meaning of which is unclear – is continually shifting at the will of the BAL (Riaz, 2019). It appears that the BAL-led authoritarian regime has been able to create a cultural hegemony centering around the concept – *Muktijuddher Chetona* – with the help of the media and traditional intellectuals as per the Gramscian idea. This paper seeks to explore whether the media in Bangladesh have worked as an apparatus of the BAL-led authoritarian regime to continuously develop the consent in favor of the concept *Muktijuddher Chetona* and thus helped build up the cultural hegemony to maintain the status quo i.e. the authoritarianism. The study will be guided by the following research question:

RQ: How do the Bangladeshi news media work as a hegemonic tool for the ruling Bangladesh Awami League to maintain its authoritarianism?

Method

In order to understand how the media in Bangladesh has helped the BAL-led authoritarianism gain the consent from society using the concept *Muktijuddher Chetona*, this paper uses the much-talked-about International Crimes Tribunal trial as a case study. The International Crimes Tribunal, a special national tribunal established to try those who perpetrated what the tribunal says crimes against humanity in the 1971 war of independence, is considered the beginning of “a series of authoritarian steps” by the BAL authoritarian regime (Riaz & Zaman, 2021, p. 41). Since the BAL assumed power in 2009, Bangladesh’s politics revolved around the trial of the war criminals and riding on this politics in “the form of opposing the anti-

liberation forces and demanding the trial of war criminals,” the BAL secured an unprecedented victory in 2014 general elections (Majumder, 2016, p. 43).

In light of United Nations Security Council (UNSC) sponsored International Crimes Tribunal Rwanda (ICTR) and International Crimes Tribunal Yugoslavia (ICTY), the Bangladesh government set up “International Crimes Tribunal Bangladesh (ICTB)” in 2009, to try those who committed “crimes against humanity” in the 1971 liberation war (Bose, 2005; Brass, 2010; Gill, 2003; Jacques, 2000; Mustafa, 1972; Sisson & Rose, 1990; Zaheer, 1994). The domestic tribunal tried a dozen of key opposition political figures, including former ministers and Members of Parliament, and awarded most of them either with death sentence or with life imprisonment, for their alleged involvement in the crimes against humanity during the 1971 war. The tribunal sentenced ten top leaders of opposition Bangladesh Jamaat-e-Islami and two top leaders of the country’ main opposition -- Bangladesh Nationalist Party (BNP) -- by 2013, either to death or to life imprisonment (Gidley & Turner, 2018, p. 61). The BNP’s key ally in the government BJI is the largest Islamist party in the country (Rahman, 2019; Riaz, 2021). The eight top leaders from the opposition camp were executed by 2014 which took the center stage in the political debate in Bangladesh. The trial, which earned a huge controversy from international observers, has stood out to be a watershed moment for Bangladesh’s politics. With the execution of half a dozen opposition political figures, who were well-known for their anti-Indian politics (Rahman, 2019; Riaz, 2021), Bangladesh’s politics has essentially got a one-party political system (Milam, 2019; Milam, 2014) ever since (Mallet, 2013; Ruud & Hasan, 2022).

As the epistemological premise of the trial is the very concept of *Muktijuddher Chetona* and the BAL regime drummed up the support for the trial using *Muktijuddher Chetona*, the trial is a good marker to understand how the media paved the path for the BAL regime to garner its

support for the trial, particularly at a time when the fairness of the trial is in question. While international observers and commentators, including the United Nations (UN), have called the trials “flawed” (Bass, 2016; Bergman, 2015; Billah, 2021; Cadman et al., 2018; Chopra, 2015; D’Costa, 2015; Fazi et al., 2018; Haque, 2018; Human Rights Watch, 2016; Mallet, 2013; Mollah, 2020; Ramachandran, 2013; Rapp, 2015; Razzaq, 2015), many others have alleged that it is an attempt of the ruling BAL – a pro-Indian political party (Ghosh, 1993; Jacques, 2000; Kumar, 2019) – to settle a score (Fair, 2019; Jalil, 2010; Sen, 2012) by crushing down the opposition political parties -- Bangladesh Jamaat-e-Islami (BJI) and its ally Bangladesh Nationalist Party (BNP) which are known for their anti-Indianism (Rahman, 2019; Riaz, 2021). This study will do a textual analysis of news articles and articles from a set of selected media house in a qualitative approach, to understand whether they supported the government narrative in their coverage of the trial. The textual analysis will essentially examine how they frame the events surrounding the trial to understand whether they have upheld the spirit of the liberation -- *Muktijuddher Chetona* -- in their coverage or whether they questioned the lack of fairness in the trial.

Textual analysis is a mechanism to decode primarily the intended meaning of the text examining sense-making practices (Mckee, 2003). For Mackee, textual analysis is making “educated guesses about how audiences interpret texts” (p. 27) or in other words, figuring out “what interpretations people are likely to make of texts” (p. 80).” He argues that although there are always many possible description interpretations of each text, there isn’t an “infinite number of reasonable interpretations of any given text at a given time in a given place” (p. 80). He, however, warned that when we make a guess about the possible interpretation of a text, we have to put it into a certain context. Fursich (2009) argues that textual analysis of media text needs

special scholarly engagement as the media texts contains discursivity between encoding and decoding. For Fursich, textual analysis is a qualitative analysis to discern the “underlying ideological and cultural assumptions of the text” by examining text’s latent meaning and implicit patterns, keeping the certain context in view (p. 240). Van Dijk (2002) also argues that the discourse analysis or textual analysis is for discerning ideological and political dimensions of media messages. Calling each of the news reports a schemata, Van Dijk suggests that the researchers should look deeply into text’s cognitive approach by dissecting its semantics, its rhetoric, its stylistics, its linguistics, and its semiotics. He is also for examining possible implications of the text to discern its ideological and political assumptions.

This paper plans to select a dozen of top largest circulated newspapers for understanding their coverage of the tribunal’s trial. Using purposive sampling approach, major news articles and news articles on the tribunal trial that appeared in the dailies from July 2013 and December 2013, would be collected, to keep the sample manageable. Major news article means important story of the day. The rationale behind choosing the July-December 2013 time period is that the news stories of this period would give us strong and discernible knowledge about the contrast of media coverage of the tribunal by dailies having opposing views. The tribunal was set up on March 25, 2010 and the first convict by the tribunal – opposition Jamaat-e-Islami leader Abdul Quader Molla, was executed on December 12, 2016, just four days before the country’s Victory Day. The execution led to a widespread violence across the country, killing at least five people (Burke & Hammadi, 2013).

Keeping the ideological and political assumptions in view, this study has conceptualized three frames building on the model of the interpretive framing process laid out by Reese and Lewis (2009) and after a primary scrutiny of several news reports. While investigating how the

War on Terror, a label assigned by the US administration, has been “absorbed into media (and therefore public) discourse,” Reese and Lewis argue that the US media were “active participants in propagating” the ‘War on Terror’ label in three ways – just transmitting the label, reifying the label and naturalizing the label. The defined transmittal frame as a frame which simply transmit the label War on Terror in the words of the authorities concerned, either quoted or paraphrased. In this frame, the media organization did not become a direct part of propagating the label as they said: “So when the War on Terror is mentioned in news texts, it is often as a straightforward statement of policy fact.” The second frame they have defined is Reification. In this frame, the media organization presented a contested policy idea as an accepted material fact. In this frame, the media organization becomes “uncritically routine, taking the frame on its own terms.” And in the third frame what they called naturalization frame, the news frame fully internalized the label (War on Terror label in this case) with a “taken-for-granted description” of the event. News and editorial references naturalize the frame here.

This study has slightly modified the three frames of the Reese and Lewis’s model, to fit in the purpose of the study conducted in a different setting as suggested by the primary scrutiny of the news articles. The frames are 1) Reification and naturalization frame, 2) challenger frame and 3) Transmittal and/or neutral frame or other frame. As the primary focus of this study is to examine the association between the ideological standpoint of the media organization as a whole and the frame choosing, I, while developing the frames for this study, attached importance to figuring out whether the news articles were pro-tribunal trial or anti-tribunal trial.

Reification and naturalization frame is the frame which directly or indirectly reifies and naturalizes the government label of the tribunal trial that the accused committed the crimes against humanity in 1971 war and they should be punished.

Challenger frame is the frame which challenges the government label and tries to establish that the government is holding the trial as a part of its political vendetta. The challenger frame is operationalized by the following items.

Transmittal and/or neutral or other frame is the frame which only transmits the label or information objectively without participating in propagating any ideas or ideals or label or more clearly, without participating in propaganda by either side -- propaganda against the tribunal trial or in favor of the tribunal trial.

The frames were developed based on the variables mentioned in the following a-priori coding scheme (Table 1).

Table 1: A Priori Coding Scheme

Frame	Variables
<i>Reification and naturalization</i>	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> <li data-bbox="493 1079 1443 1192">1. News article portrays - directly or indirectly/ explicitly or implicitly - the accused as war criminals <li data-bbox="493 1226 1443 1272">2. News article promotes the trial by describing its importance <li data-bbox="493 1306 1443 1419">3. News article has taken for granted the perception that the accused are war criminals what the government/ruling camp campaigned. <li data-bbox="493 1453 1443 1566">4. News article criticizes those who pointed out flaws in the ICT/ICT laws <li data-bbox="493 1600 1443 1646">5. News article propagates message calling for the trial of war criminals <li data-bbox="493 1680 1443 1703">6. News article that apparently goes in favor of the tribunal trial.

Challenger frame

1. News article portrays – directly or indirectly/explicitly or implicitly—that the accused are not war criminals
2. News article points out various flaws in the ICT/ICT laws, focuses on government’s political vendetta
3. News articles propagates messages/statements critical of the trial
4. News article focuses on various anomalies in the verdict/trial process
5. News article that apparently goes against the tribunal trial.

*Transmittal
and/or neutral or
other*

1. News article does not portray - directly or indirectly - the accused as war criminals
 2. It just quoted the terms “war criminals” as said by sources/others
 3. News articles neither propagates the “trial of war criminals” as “prerequisite” for justice for today’s society as campaigned by the ruling camp nor any message that oppose the trial
 4. News article neither subscribes to the government label of the accused being war criminal nor challenges the label
 5. News article that neither apparently goes against the tribunal trial nor goes in favor of the tribunal trial.
 6. Nonetheless, if a news article appears to go against the tribunal trial by any means no matter whether the other conditions here suggests otherwise should be considered a challenger frame and if a news article appears to go in favor of the tribunal trial by any means no matter whether the other conditions here suggests otherwise should
-

be considered a reification and naturalization frame.

Conclusion

A quick look over a dozen of articles from several newspapers show that the most of the newspapers in their coverage of the trial upheld the concept of *Muktijuddher Chetona* and appeared to have avoided asking questions consciously about the lack of fairness of the trial. This shows that the media helped develop the cultural hegemony centering around the concept of *Muktijuddher Chetona*. Cultural hegemony dwarfs people's intellectual ability. It creates a social schema. People cannot think of anything beyond going that schema and thus they cannot ask questions about the unfairness happening in society. This cultural hegemony essentially gives the authoritarian regime a kind of rhetorical legitimacy or 'subconscious consent' in Gramsci's words. The study findings would help us understand the reason/s behind the sustenance of an authoritarian regime, particularly from a Bangladesh-like context, apart from reinforcing the idea of Gramsci's cultural hegemony about a century after it was originally laid out and for a different social context. The study findings also help us better understand exactly what a role the media is playing in the ground when the journalism is often boasted to be instrumental for a democratic, inclusive society.

Limitations and Future Research

The biggest limitation of the study is that this is focused only on a single phenomenon. Before reaching a conclusion about this, the role of media should be understood in respect to several key phenomena of the time. One of the key tools that the autocracy in Bangladesh used to bulldoze the opposition has been extra-judicial killing and enforced disappearance. Various human rights organizations estimate that several hundreds of people were forcibly disappeared in

the last one decade while several hundreds of opposition activists were killed, either during the street protests or in the name of cross-fires. And the BAL-led regime wanted to create a narrative that killing “militants” or “Jamaat-Shibir” extra-judicially is not a big deal or disappearance of anti-liberation elements is not a big deal and is nothing with the issue of law and order. Media role in regard to these extra-judicial killings and enforced disappearances could have been a good indicator to understand whether the media have also supported the BAL to create the hegemonic ideology, but issues relating with data collection and analyses has made the examination of this phenomenon beyond the scope of this study. Future Research should focus on the role of the media and the intelligentsia in all other phenomena that construct the social culture as a whole.

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